

UTILIZING STUDENT-CENTERED CLASS ACTIVITIES AMONG BUSINESS MANAGEMENT STUDENTS IN THE NEW NORM OF LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

The Department of Management Studies' Bachelor of Science in Business Management (BSBM) program envisioned continual progress in teaching-learning delivery and faculty practices, particularly in the use of Learning Management System. The researchers attempted to explore the implementation of student-centered activities in discussion-delivery proper through G-Suite (Workspace) LMS in order to improve the transfer of knowledge and skills to the students. This action research also serves as a catalyst to the enhancement in the strategies of every faculty of higher education institutions. The study utilized mixed research designs in the conduct of the study. The researchers implemented student-centered strategies and evaluated against traditional teacher-centered lecture type of activity. The study revealed that there are insignificant differences among variables between interventions. Moreover, challenges were identified such as restricted time and learning environment among others. The researchers crafted recommendations for the enhancement of learning experience of business management learners.

Keywords: Cavite State University; instructional delivery; learning experience; mixed research designs; student-centered activity;

INTRODUCTION

Cavite State University (CvSU) – Cavite College of Arts and Trades moves forward with outcome-based education (OBE) as a forefront strategy in addressing instruction and curriculum designs for various programs it offers. Moreover, the university geared its operation to address the status quo of educational format amidst the prevailing pandemic for the reason that it has mobi-

lized its resources and yielded to a flexible approach in instruction delivery, in which the utilization of a Learning Management System (LMS) was adopted. Noting that the existence of making the teaching process more interactive and vibrant for the students becomes challenging in the utilization of LMS (Abug, Mendoza, and Tadeo, 2021).

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(BSBM) program envisioned continual progress in teaching-learning delivery and faculty practices, particularly in the use of LMS. This drives the researchers' desire to investigate the many facets possible through the LMS in order to improve students' motivation and engagement, as well as their recall of concepts and ideas, using the teacher's current intervention and facilitation.

Thus, the researchers attempted to explore the implementation of student-centered activities in discussion-delivery proper through G-Suite LMS in order to improve the transfer of knowledge and skills to the students. This action research also serves as a catalyst for the enhancement of the strategies of every faculty member of a higher education institution.

ACTION RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

Generally, this action research aimed to determine the effect of student-centered teaching and learning activities in instructional delivery process among BSBM students of CvSU – CCAT.

Specifically the researchers aimed to:

1. design and implement student-centered teaching and learning activities in instructional delivery process using LMS;
2. evaluate the implemented student-centered teaching and learning activities in instructional delivery process using LMS in terms of;
 - a. cognitive domain;
 - b. affective domain;
 - c. psychomotor domain; and
3. identify challenges in the implementation of student-centered teaching and learning activities using LMS; and
4. craft possible action plan to address the challenges encountered in the conduct of learning intervention.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Online learning is becoming the most advantageous educational alternative among higher education learners nowadays. As this becomes popular to students as well as faculty, implementation moves faster beyond preparation. Studies uncovered several issues that could avert the effectiveness of online learning among stakeholders. And though designing an effective online course is necessary, preparation and focusing on engaging instruction is likewise important. Understanding the principles behind effective teacher and student

engagement is required to improve the online learning environment among stakeholders in higher educational institutions (Abernathy and Thornburg, 2020). Moreover, in facilitating an online class, the role of instructional strategies serve as a vital tool. Multiple factors such as getting students' feedback, having flexible teaching and evaluation of policies help to improve remote learning. Furthermore, providing resources prior to the class creates an avenue for interactive online classes (Mahmood, 2020).

Researchers recognize the instructional gap between the teacher and the students in open and distance learning (ODL). It is indeed true that online facilitation of teachers is still a vital component of ODL as it provides meaningful interaction between lecturers and students. This was investigated in the study of Adesina (2020), as the facilitators have a strategic role in content development and delivery in an ODL. The study found that lecturers have a high level of acceptance and perceived ease of use of online facilitation, which implies that it should be integrated into ODL. More so, facilitators considered the platform an easy channel to engage students in instructional delivery. This supports the study of Onyema, Deborah, Alsayed, Naveed, and Sanober (2019), who found that the application of online discussion forums is effective in student-teacher interactions, communication, and assimilating information related to school activities. Moreover, the role of the teacher is to facilitate and stimulate class participation and attract attention, which is literally important. Some factors that provide limitations to the success of online discussion forums are poor power supply, teacher and student commitment, abusive posts, delayed feedbacks, poor internet connectivity, and time constraints.

The potential impact of students' participation in multiple learning styles on their academic performance was studied by Baragash and Al-Samarraie (2018). The study specifically focused on the effects of involving students in three learning modes: face-to-face learning (F2F), learning management systems (LMS), and online learning (WBL). Experienced college students assessed their views on these three models. Results showed that students participating in the F2F model have a significant positive impact on their participation in the LMS and WBL models. Findings also revealed that the LMS has a positive impact on student performance. Moreover, LMS time and tool utilization had a positive impact on students' learning performance in the blended learning environment. Hence, the study proved that the dif-

ferent teaching methods are effective in the development of college students' learning. Furthermore, Olelewe and Okwor (2017) explored studying at a higher education institution in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study focused on teachers' perceptions of interactive whiteboards adapted in their instructional delivery. The findings revealed that the majority of teachers thought interactive whiteboards were an important information and communication technology (ICT) tool that should be used in higher education. However, the study found that due to a lack of institutional support and insufficient energy supply, the ICT technology required for effective use of the interactive whiteboard is very insufficient, which is the main obstacle for teachers to using ICT. As a result, students in most courses have poor academic performance. More so, teachers need to be retrained to familiarize them with the techniques and basic skills required to effectively use interactive whiteboards in Nigerian teaching practice.

Education and learning experiences are dynamic and should address the needs of both industry and academic competence; students' learning experiences should be addressed and developed on a continuous basis (Abug et al., 2021). Thus, the studies and research conducted by the mentioned authors provide a pathway to formulate and explore student-centered teaching learning activities to further enhance the learning experiences of business management learners at CvSU-CCAT to provide avenues of improvement and a platform for meaningful strategies in instruction delivery.

te State University-CCAT Campus. The faculty researchers brainstormed the intervention and laid assumptions that will be used. The conduct of intervention followed the planning phase were instruments and various tools for a quasi-experimental approach was employed. Evaluation was the last phase of the action study where intervention were assessed. The reflective aspect of this action was used throughout the process through observation noting.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized mixed research designs in the conduct of the study. Specifically, this action research used descriptive design to describe the participants' mean scores. Considerably, quasi-experimental approaches were used in the scaffolding of intervention and analyses among the participants through the identification of controlled and intervening groups. Moreover, inferential and observation designs were utilized to augment and support the findings of the latter design. This action research has a prior null hypothesis that there are no significant differences between the variables under study among classes with student-centered teaching and learning strategies and classes without intervention.

Additionally, the authors used likert-scale questionnaires, checklists, and field and observation notes as research instruments as a basis for data analysis. In support of calibrated and standard measures of variables, the researchers have used the motivation-matrix of the University of California Davis, Center for Educational Effectiveness as a key research instrument in this action research. The researchers used two classes, which had an average of 35 students per class.

Participants of the Study

The teachers used the two heterogeneous class of BSBM for each three lecture-subjects of BSBM program offered in the campus namely Strategic Management, Product Management, and Advertising. The first class utilized the student-centered teaching and learning strategies whilst the other class did not. Moreover, four faculty members were sourced for the teachers responses in this action research.

Adoption and Implementation Process

The learning management system (LMS) as a key delivery tool in instruction delivery is ana-

OPERATIONAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1a: Framework of the Study

This action research has utilized the action-reflective framework to conduct class intervention and assess its effect in the BSBM classes of Cavi-

lyzed through the researchers' collective and collaborative ideas. This study attempted to understand and explore the facets of the new normal of learning. This action research looked at the use of student-centered activities during class discussions to see what impact they had on students' cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains. Hence, suggestions of techniques and recommendations to improve class delivery in the context of business education have been made.

Figure 1b: Adoption-Evaluation Framework

The writers, as an a priori activity of this study, brainstormed potential student-centered learning methodologies. Furthermore, the proponents planned the delivery of the intervention by determining the appropriate tools to be used in the study, such as types of student-centered learning activities, topic leveling, class flow, classes to be considered, types of assessment, variables to be considered, research instruments, and intervention timeline. Considerably, the authors have the following assumptions:

- all classes under study were both heterogeneous;
- internet accessibility was almost the same;
- applied in online session; and
- Google Workspace packages were utilized as LMS.

Figure 2a: Implementation Interactive Strategies (Think, Write, Pair and Share)

Figure 2b: Implementation Interactive Strategies (Graphic Organizer)

Figure 2c: Implementation Interactive Strategies (Live Discussion Forum)

In this action research, the faculty members employed various student-centered activities, namely: think-write-pair-share, graphic organizer, and live discussion forum as interventions, vis-a-vis traditional teacher-centered strategies. The proponents have relied on the advertising, product management, and strategic management subjects at Cavite State University's CCAT Campus' Bachelor of Science in Business Management Major in Marketing Management program.

The qualitative observation techniques were aided by class recordings. Additionally, to supplement the quantitative data needs, online evaluation sheets and student assessments were given and evaluated. Finally, descriptive and inferential statistics were used to offer proper analysis and empirical observation of the intervention.

FINDINGS AND ACTION RESEARCH NARRATIVE

Intervention Assessment

Table 1. Teachers' Observation

Areas of Observa-	With Intervention	Without Intervention
Cognitive Domain	<p>Clear understanding of the students towards subjects' terminologies were observed through adequate responses of the learners to the teachers' queries.</p> <p>Concepts of the subject were understood as the students relate relevant examples in real corporate situation.</p> <p>Deeper understanding were observed through students' analytical responses towards given problem and situations in relation to subject concern.</p>	<p>Student manifested average performance as observed by their responses on teachers queries towards subject terminology.</p> <p>Students were only starting to fully grasp the subject concept and terminologies.</p> <p>Understanding of the students are based on their plain re-</p>
Affective Domain	<p>Students expressed socialization and cooperation among co-learners.</p> <p>The sharing of ideas of the students promote interactive class atmosphere.</p> <p>Student demonstrated high respect to classmates and teacher through healthy confrontation and sharing of ideas.</p> <p>Active participation and involvement were noted with enthusi-</p>	<p>Socializing and cooperation of the students were somehow not observe.</p> <p>Free discussions among students towards topic was not observe.</p>
Psychomotor Domain	<p>Students were able to follow and apply procedures and instructions of facilitator with accuracy and promptness.</p>	<p>Students were able to follow and apply procedures and instructions of facilitator with accuracy and promptness.</p>

Table 1 shows the teachers' observation among BSBM classes with and without intervention. Observations under cognitive domain were almost the same except for a more visible explanations and discussions coming from the students. Considerably, observations from the psychomotor domain were the same across experiment groups. Finally, observations from affective domain shows that the students from with intervention tend to be more interactive, expressive, and participative compared to the study group without intervention.

Table 2. Students' Response: Cognitive Domain

Category	Without Intervention	De- scriptio n	With Inter- vention	Descrip- tion	
Cognitive Do- main	Understanding of subject terminologies.	4.34	Highly Agree	4.41	Highly Agree
	Understanding of subject concept and relevance to entrepreneurship and operational scenarios.	4.38	Highly Agree	4.33	Highly Agree
	Linking of subject concepts with the view of today's competitive market.	4.39	Highly Agree	4.36	Highly Agree
	Understanding subject concepts with marketing concepts and principles.	4.42	Highly Agree	4.42	Highly Agree
Grand Mean	4.38	Highly Agree	4.38	Highly Agree	

Table 2 showcases students' response under cognitive domain. Nominally the mean ranges were the same across experimental groups and is noted with the same grand mean for both classes. Additionally, descriptive values were the same with highly agree responses across observation groups. The results from the observation groups were almost similar because it can be attributed to the same business-cognitive competency delivered through traditional (teacher-centered) and student-centered class groups. As traditional approaches can be very rigid through lectures and were teachers act as main player, and the student-centered designs though interactive in nature, were constrained by technology and mobility issues, hence the theoretical arguments that student-centered is more conducive as far as cognitive aspect is considered was not affirmed as far as this action research is concerned.

Table 3. Students' Response: Affective Domain

Category	Without Intervention	De- scriptio n	With Inter- vention	De- scriptio n	
Affective Do- main	Socializing with classmates and other colleagues.	4.39	Highly Agree	4.49	Highly Agree
	Cooperating peacefully and amicably with classmates or group mates.	4.42	Highly Agree	4.41	Highly Agree
	Empathizing with classmates during discussions and idea confrontation.	4.34	Highly Agree	4.40	Highly Agree
	Being Reflective on the consequences of decisions that the class will make.	4.36	Highly Agree	4.37	Highly Agree
Grand Mean	4.38	Highly Agree	4.41	Highly Agree	

Table 3 presents the students response under affective domain. Generally the mean range values were on the same category. Considerably, most of the mean values from the class with intervention are higher compared to the class without intervention. Especially with the socialization variable under this domain with a mean difference of 0.10. Additionally, descriptive values were the same with highly agree responses across observation groups. The results of this table affirms the qualitative results of the teacher observers that student-centered creates a more interactive and participative atmosphere in online class. Thus, socialization is evident.

Table 4. Students' Response: Psychomotor Domain

Category		Without Intervention	Description	With Intervention	Description
Psychomotor Domain	Following the procedures and instructions of the facilitator towards the subject.	4.45	Highly Agree	4.47	Highly Agree
	Application the subject skill in conceptualization of plan.	4.45	Highly Agree	4.41	Highly Agree
	Grand Mean	4.45	Highly Agree	4.44	Highly Agree

Table 4 shows the students' responses under psychomotor domain. Generally, the mean ranges were almost the same across experimental group. Considerably, descriptive values were the same with highly agree responses. This assert the qualitative result of teacher observer that both strategy (student-centered and traditional approach) leads to the same output of creating interaction among learners.

Table 5. Significant Difference of Students' Response: Cognitive Domain

Category		Coefficient	p-value	Significance
Psychomotor Domain	Understanding of subject terminologies.	0.819	0.414	Insignificant
	Understanding of subject concept and relevance to entrepreneurship and operational scenarios.	0.552	0.582	Insignificant
	Linking of subject concepts with the view of today's competitive market.	0.375	0.709	Insignificant
	Understanding subject concepts with marketing concepts and principles.	0.013	0.989	Insignificant

Table 5 shows the significant difference under cognitive domain among the experimental groups. All the variables under study have p-values higher 0.05 thus are all insignificant. The researchers thereby accept the null hypotheses that there is no significant difference concerning cognitive domain between classes with intervention and classes without. Hence, the researchers found that that there is no causality of intervention on the experimental group under interactive activities using the online platform.

Table 6. Significant Difference of Students' Response: Affective Domain

Category		Coefficient	p-value	Significance
Affective Domain	Socializing with classmates and other	1.188	0.237	Insignificant
	Cooperating peacefully and amicably with classmates or	0.135	0.893	Insignificant
	Empathizing with classmates during discussions and idea	0.607	0.545	Insignificant
	Being Reflective on the consequences of decisions that the	0.059	0.953	Insignificant

Table 6 reveals the significant difference under affective domain among the experimental groups. All the variables under study have p-values higher 0.05 thus are all insignificant. The researchers thereby accept the null hypotheses that there is no significant difference concerning affective domain between classes with intervention and classes without. Thus, the researchers found that that there is no causality of intervention on the experimental group under interactive activities using the online platform as far as the affective domain is concerned.

Table 7. Significant Difference of Students' Response: Psychomotor Domain

Category		Coefficient	p-value	Significance
Psychomotor Domain	Following the procedures and instructions of the facilitator towards the subject.	.201	.841	Insignificant
	Application the subject skill in conceptualization of plan.	.389	.698	Insignificant

Table 7 showcases the significant difference under psychomotor domain among the experimental groups. All the variables under study have p-values higher 0.05 thus are all insignificant. The researchers thereby accept the null hypotheses that there is no significant difference concerning psychomotor domain between classes with intervention and classes without. Thereby, the researchers found that that there is no causality of intervention on the experimental group under interactive activities using the online platform as far as the psychomotor domain is concerned.

Figure 3. Assessment Scores of Students

Figure 3 shows the assessment scores of students at the end of the class session. Generally, students from classes with and without intervention performed at almost the same level based on the given assessment.

Table 7. Teachers' Observation: Challenges

The one hour prescribed online session is not enough to maximize the potential of providing student-centered learning activity.
Students and teachers were experiencing poor internet connectivity during the session.
Familiarity in the usage of applications of the students.
Some students' learning environment is not conducive for learning.

Table 7 shows the challenges that were observe by the teachers. The key challenge observed by the faculty members was that the time prescribed by the university is not enough to conduct interactive learning strategies.

CONCLUSION

The authors have adopted and utilized students-centered teaching and learning activities in instructional delivery among BSBM students of Cavite State University - CCAT Campus, the authors conclude that:

1. the selected faculty members of the Department of Management Studies designed and implemented student-centered teaching and learning strategies namely think-write-pair-share, graphic organizer, and live discussion forum in the instructional delivery process of BSBM students using G-suite LMS;
2. the implementation of student-centered teaching and learning activity in instructional delivery process provides insignificant differences in terms of cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domain numerically speaking. However, through observation affective domain is highly visible in student-centered teaching activity; and
3. the faculty researchers have identified the following key challenges:
 - the one hour prescribed online session is not enough to maximize the potential of providing student-centered learning activity;
 - students and teachers were experiencing poor internet connectivity during the session.
 - familiarity in the usage of applications of the students; and
 - some students' learning environment is not conducive for learning.

RECOMMENDATION

The researchers recommend the following:

1. increase in number of hours for class online session and maximizing the one and a half hour partial session or a 3 hour contact hours per week aligned with flexible learning approaches utilized by the program;
2. teachers should be aware of devices that the students are using to plan student-centered activities that utilizes tools that are accessible, compatible and data friendly;
3. a report of status of the internet connectivity of students may be provided and submitted to the university for their actions to be coordinate with proper authorities for their interventions, possible linkages and partnerships;

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4. encourage the learners to find an environment that will be conducive for their online session learning; and
5. undertake future action researches concerning the efficiency and efficacy of this type of intervention and other variables that might influence the learning experiences of business students for further understanding and improvement of strategies.

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